

SEARCH FOR THE SELF IN PICO IYER'S *THE LADY AND THE MONK:*
FOUR SEASONS IN KYOTO

Research Scholar

Kirti Choudhary

Dept. of English, Maharshi Dayanand
University, Rohtak, Harvna

Research Guide

Dr. Rashmi Malik

Department of English and Foreign Languages

Abstract –

*The current paper focuses on Pico Iyer's autobiographical work *The Lady and The Monk: Four Seasons in Kyoto*. It is an imaginative and lyrical narrative of a year in Kyoto, full of witty and precise insights about the country and its people. Iyer was introduced to a lifestyle where he had to constantly switch homes from a young age. He was born in Oxford, England, to Indian parents, and grew up between California and Britain for academic studies. The writer's own hybridity and multicultural upbringing gives him the ability to analyse and refigure Japan which Homi K. Bhabha refers to as the power of 'rearticulation', allowing him to negotiate oppositions rather than submitting to their fundamental claims or becoming trapped within their binary representations. Iyer explores his complicated relationship with identity and the quest for belonging. His narrative conceptualises the self where identity is constantly in flux. It focuses on the concepts of cultural identity and cultural hybridity and explores the interrelationship between these two from the experience of the writer.*

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Key Words - Pico Iyer, identity, hybridity, Homi K. Bhabha, cultural identity, Japanese culture

Introduction

Culture resonates in every part of life. Culture is the collection of values, beliefs, and behaviours that are learned and shared by a group of people. It provides the group with an identity, assures their existence, and increases their sense of belonging. In a way, culture defines us and we define culture. E.P Thompson defines culture as “when some men, as a result of common experiences (inherited or shared), feel and articulate the identity of their interests as between themselves, and as against other men whose interests are different from (and usually opposed to) theirs”. (Storey 64).

There's an intricate connection between the culture and identity. Identity defines an

individual's notion of the self. It represents the context through which an individual perceives himself. The use of language, social structures, gender, and cultural traditions work all together to construct identities. When mixed together, cultural identity represents an individual's connection to a specific community or culture. The procedure includes discovering and understanding conventions, traditions, language, religion, lineage, perception, and the societal framework of a culture. The individuals usually adopt their culture's ideas, norms, and social behaviours and identify with them. In this way, culture gets established in their self-concept.

Pico Iyer in his travelogue *The Lady and the Monk*, focuses on these questions of self-representation, identity, belonging and the challenges posed in fitting into the cultural framework of the Japanese world. He records events and develops them in the form of a diary of a traveller who's fascinated with the idea of Japan. In Iyer's journey of self-discovery, he seeks a connection with the alienating place he has consciously chosen to call 'home'. The writer redirects his attention from the known idea of home to the unknown home with which he has felt a connection. The present paper aims to study the concepts of cultural identity and cultural hybridity and explore the interrelationship between these two from the experience of the writer.

Identity and Hybridity

Iyer, at the beginning of the book, reveals that since he was a child, he associated Japan as an 'imaginary homeland' and in his imagination, the concept of Zen and women of the Heian era held an influential identity that was highlighted and emphasised throughout his youth. Iyer's compulsion for Japan has increased over the years with the urge to unify Japan's two contradicting faces, the contemporary high-tech country and the lyrical contemplative land depicted in its ancient literature. He finally decided to put his visions of Japan to the test and "pass through the looking glass of dreams" to "the private Japan, and the emotional Japan--the lunar Japan...that I had found in the poems of women and monks." (Iyer 7)

Iyer interacted with both residents and foreigners to understand everything he could about Zen and Japanese society from the inside. Iyer attempted to acquire the intermediary shared setting when 'gaijin' (non-Japanese) accepts and comprehends Japanese culture and is accepted in return. The writer, to fit in, mirrors the cultural values, characteristics and language of the dominant culture. This creates an ambivalent space of being almost the same but not similar, shaped through mimicry. The theorist Stuart Hall, in 'Cultural Identity and Diaspora' *Transatlantic Literary Studies: A Reader* explored that cultural identity is both about 'being' and 'becoming', 'belonging as much to the future as it does to the past'. Hall describes identity to be constantly transforming and transcending the boundaries of space and time. Hall asserts the idea that cultural identities are not

fixed or stable, but may be altered by interruptive forces with the ability to deconstruct and recreate who we think we are. Iyer's desire to write about himself in a

foreign place and becoming a part of the foreign culture occurs parallelly with the recognition that the strands of belonging and not belonging are inextricably woven into the existing cultural, national, and ethnic identity. And as he engages in this multidimensional exercise, he puts 'the self' in motion. Iyer uses the instrument of everchanging seasons to define the continuous change,

in Japan, stages in life seemed as rigorously demarcated as the hours of the day: just as people changed kimono or bracelets with the seasons, just as restaurants served different kinds of rice, or tea, according to the time of year — customs that we, not imprisoned by them, could afford to and enchanting — so Japanese people had to change roles and identity on cue, with the seasons of their lives. (100)

Through this exploration of transition, Iyer acquires an unstable identity and becomes a part of the process. Iyer's significant South-Asian appearance can't be stereotyped within the "typical Westerner" norm. To the writer's acknowledgement, he is: "a mysterious Indian, history-steeped Brit, fun-loving Californian, romantic loner, wandering writer, sometimes monk"(192). Iyer expands the divisions between the Japanese and the Western by invoking cultural nostalgia on his travels between his 'naturalised' home, Britain, and his imagined home, Japan. Iyer's non-white identity dilutes the cultural distinction between the Japanese and the Western, leading to the emergence of a renewed construction between 'gaijin' and Japan.

During his journey, Iyer meets a Japanese housewife Sachiko with whom he develops a fond relationship and learns about the hidden struggle of the Japanese women, facing the same challenges as him. Sachiko is a single mother who adheres to the traditional Japanese social norms and conventions. As the friendship between Iyer and Sachiko grew, they exchanged information about the contrasts and similarities between their cultures, which made them realise that they had lived completely different lives. Iyer, for example, had never stayed in one town for an extended period of time. He'd been travelling all over the world. Sachiko, on the other hand, had never left Japan. She spends the majority of her time at home, doing chores. Iyer recalls,

All nine-year-old schoolgirls, say, or forty-five-year-old executives — were encouraged to look, or at least dress, alike by a society that wanted them to conform to an anonymous model, to become generic, in a sense. A sense of interchangeable identity not only helped to enforce unity; it also made one parent's daughter seem almost like another's, and thus enforced a larger sense of duty. So when Sachiko talked of her "mother part" and "wife part" and "daughter part," ... the absoluteness of the way in which people here were both

parts and partitions — and parts, in fact, were inflexibly partitioned. (101)

For Sachiko, the stereotypical idea of identity for Japanese women is encouraged by societal norms and conventions, which she has moulded herself into over the years. In certain ways, Sachiko is nearly Iyer's Japanese counterpart. Iyer's understanding of Japan is focused on classical literature whereas Sachiko's understanding of the West is largely based on pop music and movies. While he sees Japan as a place to discover himself, she sees the West as the land of freedom and a source of escape from her constrained life. Iyer's interpretation of their connection is mediated through the old Japanese love poetry whereas Sachiko's romance is the fulfilment of her every dream. In a way, each is a reflection of the fantasy the other holds. Iyer learns about the complexity of modern Japanese living through his connection when Sachiko opens up to Iyer about her own trials and tribulations. Sachiko's life is restricted, despite her attractiveness and cheerfulness. Her whole life, like that of many Japanese men and women, was basically planned before she was born.

Sachiko's fascination with the world beyond Japan, and her desire for knowing about 'the Other', including an attraction to all things American, assists in escaping the Japanese national restraints. Furthermore, through engaging in the commodified popular culture of the West, Sachiko's standpoint challenges the established stereotype of a typical Japanese woman. Sachiko's interest in American rock stars and her wide-eyed curiosity about the world beyond Japan makes for an intriguing establishment of her and Iyer's intercultural connection. Bhabha describes the in-between space of the cultural encounter between two cultures as the 'third space' of cultural diction. This space predominantly undermines "the binary thought and essentialist identities produced" (Bhabha 213) which deconstructs the binary of the self and 'the Other'. Additionally, it is a space of ambiguity, hesitation, and uncertainty, and it deconstructs the authentic and rooted self. Sachiko's identification as a 'follower' of the Japanese tradition rather than a 'leader' is rooted in the Japanese culture's extremely gendered norms which changes when she ultimately chooses divorce over a dysfunctional marriage. She exemplifies the non-conforming Japanese woman in a stratified and exclusionist society.

Sachiko reconnects with love and fantasies about America via Iyer's eyes, in a type of 'transcultural space'. In *The Location of Culture*, Homi K. Bhabha uses an illustration of a stairway by art historian Renee Green as a 'liminal space' that signifies a place of metaphoric exchange in two distinct cultures. In the above-mentioned work, this is depicted by the interaction between Sachiko and Iyer. In the same oeuvre, this is illustrated by the interaction between Iyer and Sachiko. In Green's words, this "interstitial passage between fixed identifications opens up the possibility of a cultural hybridity that entertains difference without an assumed or imposed

hierarchy.” (5) The concept of hybridity explains that individual identities are built up of all the different cultures with which they come in contact. When two cultures or nations meet, they exchange ideas, language, and material possessions. That exchange the process drives them to adapt and change. As a result, the act of exchange generates an ‘Other’ with which to interact and integrate identity. In the text, Sachiko's life changes because of their interactions and the impact of Westernization becomes apparent when she serves her conventional limits as a mother and wife.

Iyer’s depiction of cultural movement and the reconstruction of identity can be seen through the example of him adjusting to the Japanese culture and at the same time, Sachiko realising her identity within the Japanese culture. It proposes a deconstruction of the notion that identity is fundamentally connected to a fixed culture, time, and space, rather than emphasising identity as a process of becoming and is in continuous flux. Iyer's narration is a constructive way of self-representation that challenges origins, re-deconstructs identity, and maps diversity.

Conclusion

Pico Iyer's own hybridity and multicultural upbringing gives him the ability to analyse and reconfigure Japan which Bhabha refers to as the power of 'rearticulation', allowing him to negotiate oppositions rather than submitting to their fundamental claims or becoming trapped within their binary representations. Iyer's desire to adapt to the Japanese social construction, and the persistent efforts to break the abstract and imaginative limits of the culture while living there, provided him with the rare opportunity to experience a unique condition. Iyer claims that Japan is one of the most hybridised spaces existing around the globe. It is known for considering the entire world as a vast souvenir shop which provides pleasure, and most visitors are conscious of that. Iyer’s hybridity enables him to experience and recognize the barriers that Japan has built to maintain itself free of foreign influences, even while indiscriminately embracing cultural trends from the West. As a result, Iyer being a hybridised ‘gaijin’ also becomes a part of Japanese culture.

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